

Studies in Conjugated Imines : Reduction of Cinnamylidene Arylamines with Diborane

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Brown¹ has established the relative reactivity of diborane with various functional groups. This difference in rates of hydroboration and reduction was utilized for the selective reaction of double bond in the presence of other isolated functional group². Very little is known however about the relative reactivities of two functional groups conjugated to one another. In this area few conjugated carbonyl compounds ($>C=C-\overset{|}{C}=O$) have been studied and relative activity of $>C=C<$ and $>C=O$ functions have been established. This communication describes preferential reduction of $>C=N$ bond in the presence of $C=C$ bond with diborane ($>C=C-\overset{|}{C}=N-$).

The cinnamylidene-arylamines were prepared by condensing cinnamic aldehyde with appropriate amines. The hydroboration of cinnamylidene aniline proceeded stepwise, the azomethine group being the first group attached. When cinnamylidene aniline in tetrahydrofuran was hydroborated and the reaction mixture allowed to stand for 15 minutes and worked up as usual it gave dihydrocinnamal aniline II. The structure II is based on elemental analysis, I.R., N.M.R. and the mass spectrum. The characteristics of dihydro compounds similarly prepared are given in the Table 1

The N.M.R. Spectrum (60 MHz in $CDCl_3$) of a typical dihydro compound (II) was recorded. The olefinic protons showed up in the region 3-4 τ . The I.R. Spectrum indicated the presence of styrene bond ($CH=CH$ trans) in the region 900-1000 cm^{-1} (Table I). The styrene bond was also reduced if hydroboration was carried on for longer period. When cinnamylarylaniline (or cinnamal aniline) was hydroborated and reactants were allowed to stand overnight and then worked up hydrocinnamyl aniline (III) was obtained in 70% yield. The secondary amine was characterised through hydrochloride formation.

As for the mechanism of this reduction is concerned, it seems plausible that co-ordination of borane to the nitrogen of Schiff's bases occurs followed by an intramolecular hydride transfer from boron to carbon just analogous to as proposed for carbonyl compounds.

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I

II

III

Regarding the scope of this reaction there seems to be no interference due to substituents in the aromatic nuclei, and yields are reasonably good

EXPERIMENTAL

General procedure: Cinnamylidene arylamines were prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of cinnamaldehyde and appropriate amine in ethyl alcohol. The characteristics of these amines are recorded in Table 1. The melting points recorded agree with those reported in literature. The imines (4-5) are not already recorded in literature.

Analysis of Imine 4. M.F. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{NCl}$

	C	H	N	Cl
Calcd.	74.53	4.97	5.79	14.71
Found	74.44	4.86	5.70	14.60

Analysis of Imine 5 M.F. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{NF}$

	C	H	N	F
Calcd.	80.03	5.33	6.23	8.41
Found	79.95	5.28	6.12	8.36

General Procedure: Diborane prepared by treating a solution of sodium borohydride (2.36 gms., 9.19m.mol) in diglyme (5 ml) with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ was passed through a wash bottle containing small amount of NaBH_4 in DG (to remove traces of BF_3) into a solution of Schiff's base I-IX (10 ms. mol) in THF (20-30 ml) at 0° for ten to fifteen minutes with stirring. After this time the solvent was removed under vacuum to dryness and the residue

dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) was gently warmed for about half an hour to decompose any aminoborane which might have formed in this reaction. The removal of the solvent left a residue, the characteristics of the dihydro compounds and solvent of crystallisation are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Conjugated imines	m.p (°C)	m.p of dihydro- products (secondary amines) (m.p of picrate, °C)	Infrared absorption*	Yields (solvent of crystallisation)	Analysis	
					Calc. (%)	Found (%)
N-cinnamylidene-aniline	109	20(135)	---	90 (MeOH)	N, 12.7	12.5**
N-cinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -bromoaniline	120	89-90	CH=CH (trans) 970 cm ⁻¹ NH-3380 cm ⁻¹	100 (light petroleum)	N, 4.9 Br, 27.8	4.8 27.7
N-cinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	108	80	CH=CH (trans) 975 cm ⁻¹ NH-3375 cm ⁻¹	100 (,,)	N, 5.8 Cl, 14.6	5.7 14.5
N-cinnamylidene- <i>m</i> -chloroaniline	116	49	---	100 (,,)	N, 5.8 Cl, 14.71	5.7 14.62
N-cinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -fluoroaniline	88-89	52	---	75 (MeOH)	N, 6.23 F, 8.41	6.12 8.36
N-cinnamylidene- <i>m</i> -nitroaniline	92	115-116	---	100 (benzene- hexane, 1 : 1)	N, 5.5	5.4
N-cinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -anisidine	120	71	CH=CH (trans) 960 cm ⁻¹	90 (hexane)	N, 5.85	5.75
N-cinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -toluidine	83	39-40(140)	---	97 (hexane)	N, 6.3	6.2
N-cinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -phenetidene	110	74-75	CH=CH (trans) 965 cm ⁻¹ NH-3370 cm ⁻¹	80 (light petroleum)	N, 5.5	5.45

* Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr with a Beckman Spectrophotometer.

** Combination analysis of the picrate.

The above procedure modified by producing diborane in situ in THF gave exactly the same dihydro compounds.

In case of cinnamylidene aniline when diborane used was in excess *i.e.* double the amount as indicated in the above procedure and reaction mixture allowed to stand for 24 hrs and worked up as above gave an oil in 70% yield, a small portion of which was characterised as hydrochloride m.p. 235° (dec.)

Analysis of hydrochloride. M.F. $C_{15}H_{17}N.HCl$

	C	H	N	Cl
Calcd.	72.73	7.27	5.65	14.34
Found	72.60	7.21	5.60	14.15

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